

UO'K 581.4

ACHCHIQ QOVUN (*MOMORDICA CHARANTIA* L) NING XROMOSOMALAR TAXLILI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada *Momordica charantia* o'simligining genomidagi xromosoma taxlili o'tkazilgan bo'lib, Achchiq qovun (*Momordica charantia* L.) *Momordica* turkumiga mansub, *Momordica charantia* ning xromosomalar juda kichik va zich sitoplazmatik fon tufayli ularni bo'yash va ko'rish qiyin. Xromosomaning o'lchamlari xromosomalar soni va ushbu turning umumiy xromosoma uzunligi tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xromosoma, *Momordica charantia*, mitoz, Adobe Photoshop CS6.

ХРОМОСОМНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ДЫНИ ГОРЬКОЙ (*MOMORDICA CHARANTIA* L).

Аннотация: В данной статье проведен хромосомный анализ генома растения *Momordica charantia* Bitter Melon (*Momordica charantia* L.), относящегося к роду *Momordica*. Хромосомы *Momordica charantia* очень малы и их трудно окрашивать и визуализировать из-за плотного цитоплазматического фона. Проанализированы размеры хромосом, число хромосом и общая длина хромосом этого вида.

Ключевые слова: Chromosoma, *Momordica charantia*, митоз, Adobe Photoshop CS6.

CHROMOSOME ANALYSIS OF BITTER MELON (*MOMORDICA CHARANTIA* L).

Abstract: Chromosome analysis in the genome of *Momordica charantia* plant was carried out in this article, Bitter melon (*Momordica charantia* L.) belongs to the *Momordica* genus, the chromosomes of *Momordica charantia* are very small and because of the dense cytoplasmic background, they can be stained and visualized difficult. Chromosome sizes, number of chromosomes and total chromosome length of this species were analyzed.

Key words: Chromosoma, *Momordica charantia*, mitosis, Adobe Photoshop CS6.

Kirish. Achchiq qovun (*Momordica charantia* L.) *Momordica* turkumiga mansub, diploid xromosoma soni $2n=22$ bo'lgan muhim to'yimli sabzavot o'simligi bo'lib, o'ziga xos achchiq ta'mga ega bo'lgan pishmagan mevalari tuberkulyoz uchun yetishtiriladi. Xarakterli achchiq ta'mi "momordisin" kimyoviy moddasi mavjudligi bilan bog'liq [1]. *Momordica* ning xromosomalar juda kichik va zich sitoplazmatik fon tufayli ularni bo'yash va ko'rish qiyin. [2]. Xromosomaning o'lchamlari xromosomalar soni va ushbu turning umumiy xromosoma uzunligi tahlil qilindi.

Materiallar va uslublar. Xromosomalar sonini aniqlash uchun kamida 5 ta metafaza hisoblangan va har bir hujayraning xromosomalari bir-biridan yaxshi uzoqlashgan.

Xromosoma morfologik o'lchovlari va ideogramma yaratish uchun ishlatilgan IdeoKar1.3 [4]. Xromosoma metafazalarini yig'ish uchun KERN OPTICS S-EYE 1.10.7, xromosoma juftlarini tahlil qilish uchun Adobe Photoshop CS6 (Adobe Systems, AQSH) dasturidan foydalanilgan.

Tadqiqot natijalarining muhokamasi. Tadqiqotimiz natijalari IdeoKar dasturida ishlatiladigan xromosoma parametrlari va karotip assimetriya ko'rsatkichlarining o'lchovlari va formulalari orqali aniqladik.[4]. Xromosoma parametrlari: Qo'l nisbati $AR = L/S$, Xromosoma uzunligi $CL = L + S$, r-value S/L , Xromosomaning nisbiy uzunligi $RL\% = (CL/\sum CL) \times 100$, Sentromerik indeks $CI = S/CL$, Xromosoma turi [5]. Karyotipik parametrlar yoki assimetriya

indekslari: $F\% = (S/\sum CL) \times 100$, Gaploid komplementning umumiy xromosoma uzunligi $HCL = \sum CL$, Shaklning umumiy ulushi $TF\% = (\sum S / \sum CL) \times 100$ [6]. Karyotip assimetriyasining Arano indeksi $AsK\% = (\sum L / \sum CL) \times 100$ [3]. Xromosoma ichidagi assimetriya indeksi $A_1 = [\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i/L_i)/n]$ [7], Xromosomalararo assimetriya indeksi $A_2 = s_{CL}/x_{CL}$ [7]. Simmetriya ko‘rsatkichi $S\% = (CL_{min}/CL_{max}) \times 100$, O‘rtacha sentromerik indeks $X_{CI} = \sum CL/n$, Karyotip assimetriyasi darajasi $A = [\sum_{i=1}^n (L_i - S_i) / (L_i + S_i)]/n$ [8]. O‘rtacha sentromerik assimetriya $x_{CA} = A \times 100$, Xromosoma uzunligining o‘zgaruvchanlik koeffitsienti $CV_{CL} = (s_{CL}/x_{CL}) \times 100 = A_2 \times 100$, Sentromerik indeksning o‘zgaruvchanlik koeffitsienti $CV_{CI} = (s_{CL}/x_{CL}) \times 100$, Asimetriya indeksi $AI = (CV_{CL} \times CV_{CI})/100$ [9]. L: uzun qo‘lning uzunligi; S: qisqa qo‘lning uzunligi; i: gomologik guruh raqami; s: standart og‘ish; x: o‘rtacha; n: individual yoki taksonning gaploid xromosoma soni; S. sinf: assimetriya Stebbins toifasi [4]. *Momordica charantiana*ning xromosomalari tahlillarimizda diploid $2n=22$ bo‘ldi. Gaploid xromosomasining uzunligi 20,26 mkm, eng uzun xromosomasi 2,45 mkm, eng kichik xromosomasi 1,11 mkm ekanligi aniqlandi (1- jadval).

***Momordica charantiana*ning gaploid xromosomalarining parametirlari**

1- jadval

<i>HCL</i>	<i>TF</i>	<i>AsK%</i>	<i>S%</i>	<i>Xci</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>XcA</i>	<i>CVcl</i>	<i>CVci</i>	<i>AI</i>	<i>Stebbine</i>	<i>AI</i>	<i>A2</i>
20,26	28,8	71,2	45,2	0,28	0,45	44,50	23,77	32,44	73,26	1B	0,59	0,24
<i>N_o</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>CL</i>	<i>AR</i>	<i>r-Value</i>	<i>RL%</i>	<i>F%</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>Xromosoma turi</i>			
1	1,26	1,18	2,45	1,09	0,92	12,08	5,84	0,48	m			
2	1,53	0,79	2,32	1,93	0,52	11,43	3,89	0,34	sm			
3	1,37	0,74	2,11	1,86	0,54	10,39	3,64	0,35	sm			
4	1,79	0,63	2,42	2,83	0,35	11,95	3,12	0,26	sm			
5	1,58	0,29	1,87	6	0,17	9,22	1,43	0,15	st			
6	1,34	0,42	1,76	3,13	0,32	8,70	2,08	0,24	st			
7	1,37	0,37	1,74	3,71	0,27	8,57	1,82	0,21	st			
8	1,05	0,47	1,53	2,22	0,45	7,53	2,34	0,31	sm			
9	1,24	0,32	1,55	3,83	0,26	7,66	1,56	0,21	st			
10	1,05	0,37	1,42	2,86	0,35	7,01	1,82	0,26	sm			
11	0,842	0,26	1,11	3,2	0,31	5,45	1,3	0,24	st			

1-rasm. *Momordica charantianing* xromosoma ajratib olish va mikroskopda ko'rinishi

2-rasm. Achchiq qovun *Momordica charantianing* xromosoma tahlili. **A)** *M. charantianing* mikroskopda olingan real, **B)** tahrirlangan tasviri. **C,D)** Adobe Photoshop CS6da va IdeoKar dasturida tayyorlangan ideogrammasi.

XULOSA. Andijon viloyati sharoitida yetishtirilgan *Momordica charantia* o'simligizning molekulyar xromosomasi taxlil qilinganda uning diploid xromosomasi 22 ta ekanligi aniqlandi. IdeoKar dasturida ishlatiladigan xromosoma parametrlari va karotip assimetriya ko'rsatkichlarining o'lchovlari va formulalari orqali xromosoma tuzilishi o'rganildi.

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